

THE PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES (ESP) THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

Kismetova G.
Utegenova B.

M.Utemisov West Kazakhstan University, Uralsk, Kazakhstan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13908708>

Abstract

The use of technology plays a significant role in enhancing the learning experience of students in the field of English for Specific Purposes (ESP), where learners apply the target language in specialized professional contexts. As the demand for specialized language skills continues to grow in diverse sectors, the integration of digital tools such as e-learning platforms, mobile apps, artificial intelligence (AI), and virtual reality (VR) is becoming increasingly relevant. The research underscores the shift in pedagogical approaches, emphasizing a transition to learner-centered models driven by interactive, multimedia content. The study also explores the impact of digital technologies on learner motivation, engagement, and performance, finding that many learners appreciate the flexibility and real-world relevance that digital tools bring to ESP instruction.

Keywords: English for Specific Purposes (ESP), digital technologies in education, e-learning platforms, mobile apps for language learning, learner-centered approaches, multimedia learning

Introduction

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is a specialized course designed to help people grow their English language skills so they can go after specific careers. By sharpening their English, people who want to excel in their careers can do so in areas where English is the second language.[1] English for Specific Purposes (ESP) focuses on equipping learners with the language proficiency needed to communicate effectively in these specialized domains. Unlike general English language instruction, ESP is tailored to meet the specific linguistic requirements of particular industries, providing learners with the tools to navigate professional environments using the target language.

Digital technologies in education provide the learning process by means of electronic devices and resources. The main trend in the development of electronic technologies in teaching foreign languages is the integration of a computer, mobile phone and the Internet into a single information and communication environment.[2] The integration of digital technologies into ESP education is proving to be a key driver of innovation in language learning. Among the factors characterizing the future development of ESP, it is important to note the need to expand the scope of English for Specific Purposes, the search for further methodological approaches aimed at teaching professionally oriented and business communication, the strengthening of the methodological foundation of teaching, the search for new pedagogical conditions to ensure effective learning of ESP, and the active use of electronic learning tools.[3]

Materials and types of research

The objectives of this study are to explore the role of digital technologies in the development and enhancement of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) education, focusing on how emerging tools can address the unique needs of learners in specialized professional contexts. To examine the current use of digital technologies in ESP programs across various fields, to assess the impact of digital tools, artificial intelligence (AI),

virtual reality (VR), and augmented reality (AR) on the teaching methodologies, learner engagement, and language acquisition in ESP.

Research questions

This study aims to explore the role of digital technologies in enhancing the teaching and learning of English for Specific Purposes (ESP), focusing on the integration of digital tools into various professional fields. The following research questions guide the investigation:

1. How are digital technologies currently being integrated into ESP programs?
2. What impact do digital technologies have on learner engagement and motivation in ESP courses?
3. What challenges do educators face when integrating digital technologies into ESP instruction?

These research questions aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the opportunities and challenges that digital technologies present in the field of ESP, therefore, about 20 foreign language teachers and 74 learners from our school were involved to complete questionnaires about using digital tools for ESP and the impact of these tools on students' learning. Students were asked about their experiences with technology in language learning, with particular emphasis on how it helped them improve their ability to communicate effectively in the foreign language, focusing on the unique needs of learners in specialized professional contexts.

Tools. Several digital tools are particularly well-suited for the development of ESP:

- Learning Management Systems (LMS): Platforms like Moodle, Blackboard, and Canvas allow teachers to create customized ESP courses that include multimedia resources, assessments, and discussion forums.
- Mobile Applications: Mobile apps such as "Quizlet" and "Memrise" can be used for vocabulary acquisition in specific domains like medical or legal English. Apps like "Kahoot" and "Socratic" enable interactive quizzes that help learners retain industry-specific terminology.

- Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR): Immersive technologies like VR and AR can simulate work environments, allowing ESP learners to practice language skills in a realistic setting. For instance, medical students can engage in virtual patient interactions, while business learners can practice negotiations in a virtual boardroom.

- Online Platforms for Communication: Tools like Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and Google Meet are vital for conducting live classes and virtual exchanges, which can include discussions, presentations, and even mock interviews tailored to specific professions.

First of all, a questionnaire was distributed to foreign language teachers to investigate the types of technology they implement in ESP classes, to stimulate and motivate their students interest, to enhance their motivation, engagement, and performance. Teachers' answers were different but most of them tend to use digital tools and integrating them is fundamentally important in ESP classes, because there are a various students with diverse interests and needs. For those using technology, additional questions focused on the specific tools and platforms employed, such as interactive simulations and multimedia resources, to enhance students' English skills.

Recognizing the significant role of digital technology in ESP classes, especially in language acquisition, the following needs arise for its integration and establishment in the daily learning process:

- Digital tools, based on the needs and prerequisites of all staff working with learners, must be accessible to them;
- The digital learning resources used in teaching ESP should align with educational content and lead to the effective use of technologies;
- Digital technologies should be used to facilitate the working conditions of staff in organizing and managing the teaching and learning process.[4]

Furthermore, some interviews were carried out with teachers who actively integrated technology into their foreign language classrooms. The aim was to explore the role of digital technologies in the development and enhancement of ESP, how digital tools can support learners' necessity in specialized professional contexts. Some teachers were interviewed about effectiveness of digital technologies including multimedia resources (videos, simulations, and podcasts), online learning platforms, language learning apps, and virtual classrooms. Interviewees said that these tools offer learners access to authentic materials, industry-specific vocabulary, and interactive content, all of which are essential in ESP for tailoring lessons to specific professional or academic contexts. But some of them prefer blended learning approaches that combine face-to-face and digital instruction that are also becoming common, they can significantly increase learner engagement and motivation in ESP courses by offering interactive and personalized learning experiences.

ESP involves the intensive development of teaching and assessment technologies through the widespread use of multimedia tools, electronic courses, textbooks, and the search for effective methods of distant

learning aimed at professionally oriented communication with specialists at the international level.[3]

Moreover, to collect data from learners, a separate questionnaire was used. This aimed to evaluate their point of view on how digital technologies had affected to increase their skills in ESP lessons. The questionnaire asked students to reflect on their experiences using digital tools and how these tools had helped improve their language proficiency, particularly in areas such as speaking and writing.

Procedure

The study focused on comprehension how far technology can be effectively implemented into foreign language teaching at the school level to level up students' skills in ESP lessons. A various approaches were used to identify teachers and students preferences and experiences in using new technologies and collecting some data about it. The objectives were two: to determine the tools used by teachers to develop ESP and to evaluate the challenges and benefits associated with using these tools in foreign language classrooms.

Enter the questionnaire

Teachers and students from various were chosen for taking part and engaging into the study. Questionnaires were given out to foreign language teachers to collect data on their experience with technological tools in teaching, and short interviews were carried out with selected teachers to grasp deeper insights, feedback about their use of technology. The study also surveyed students to understand their perceptions of how these tools helped them engage in ESP classes.

Conducting an interview

For the qualitative part of the study, ten teachers who incorporated technology into their classrooms were interviewed in-depth. The short interview format provided flexibility, enabling a deeper exploration of how these teachers implemented technology and their perspectives on its impact. The interviews were recorded, transcribed, and, in two instances, translated into English for analysis. The goal of these interviews was to collect detailed insights into the benefits and challenges of using technology to develop discursive competence.

Data analysis

Data from the questionnaires and interviews were analyzed using a phenomenological approach, enabling the researchers to uncover shared themes and patterns in the experiences of both teachers and students. The qualitative data from the interviews were coded, leading to the identification of various topics, such as the advantages of using technology focusing on ESP aims and the difficulties related to its implementation. The findings were summarized to offer a clear overview of how technology influences the development of ESP among foreign language learners.

Research results

The survey results identified two groups of teachers: those who consistently used technology to promote ESP education while some teachers did not. However most of them actively incorporated technology, such as interactive platforms and multimedia resources, into their teaching. These teachers had been using technological tools for ages, leveraging them to create online

materials, offer interactive exercises, and support student engagement in ESP. They reported spending several hours each week developing lessons aimed at improving students' language proficiency needed to communicate effectively in these specialized domains. In contrast, a few number of teachers pointed to unfamiliarity with technological tools and a lack of time as the main reasons for not integrating them into their instruction.

The use of digital technology in the field of pedagogy is not limited to acquiring technical skills, but requires the optimal use of its achievements and changing everyday teaching practices. The main goal during skill development is for the student to engage in the given task independently. Now, in the learning process, the teacher's role is no longer as dominant as before; instead, the student's responsibility, initiative, and active participation come to the forefront. The teacher acts as a consultant. This is a flexible, student-centered process.[4]Конец формы Despite the fact that digital technologies are mostly used for ESP learners, their integration into ESP also presents challenges. Issues such as equitable access to technology, teacher training, and the need for further research on the long-term impact of digital tools on learner outcomes must be addressed to fully realize the potential of these innovations.

Advantages of using digital technologies for the developing of ESP.

The development of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) through digital technologies offers several significant advantages, particularly in enhancing the learning experience and addressing the specific needs of professional and academic learners. Some of the key benefits include:

- **Personalized Learning;** Digital tools allow educators to design ESP courses that focus on industry-specific vocabulary and scenarios. Platforms with adaptive learning features can adjust content based on individual learners' progress and needs.
- **Interactive and Engaging Learning Methods;** Gamification: Tools such as quizzes, games, and interactive exercises (e.g., Kahoot or Quizlet) make learning more engaging and help reinforce vocabulary and concepts in an enjoyable manner.
- **Collaboration and Communication.** Virtual Collaboration: Digital tools (e.g., Microsoft Teams, Zoom, Slack) allow learners to collaborate and communicate in real-time with peers and instructors, simulating professional communication environments and enhancing their language proficiency.
- **Immediate Feedback and Progress Tracking.** Real-Time Feedback: Online assessments and interactive tools provide immediate feedback on assignments, quizzes, and exercises, allowing learners to identify areas for improvement quickly.

These advantages highlight the potential for digital technologies to transform the way ESP is delivered, making it more accessible, flexible, and effective in preparing learners for specific professional or academic contexts.

The uniqueness of distance learning lies in the fact that it eliminates the individual factor in teaching and allows students to use multiple channels for receiving

information, neutralizing the subjective factor under the teacher's supervision. On the other hand, like any form of education, distance learning also has disadvantages that significantly affect the quality of the outcome. The possibility of mastering the English language using distance learning methods is doubtful, as this process has its own peculiarities associated with teaching the variety of speech activities.[6]

The disadvantages of using digital tool for ESP. The development of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) through digital technologies, while offering numerous advantages, also presents several challenges and disadvantages. These obstacles can hinder the effective integration of digital tools into ESP learning and teaching. Some of the key disadvantages include:

- **Digital Literacy Gaps;** lack of Technical Skills: Both teachers and learners may lack the necessary digital literacy to effectively use online platforms, applications, or tools. Instructors may require training on how to integrate digital resources into their lessons, while learners might struggle to navigate unfamiliar technologies.
- **Limited Access to Technology;** Digital Divide: Not all learners have access to the necessary technology, such as smartphones, tablets, computers, or reliable internet connections. This is especially problematic in rural or economically disadvantaged areas, where learners may struggle to access digital ESP resources.
- **Quality and Availability of ESP-Specific Content;** lack of Specialized Content: Many existing digital platforms and apps are designed for general English learning and may not offer sufficient industry-specific materials for ESP. Developing quality, profession-specific content can be time-consuming and costly, making it less accessible to teachers and institutions.
- **Generic Platforms:** Digital platforms may lack customization options to cater to the diverse needs of specific professional fields, limiting their effectiveness in teaching specialized terminology or contextual language use.

Student Reference Information and Experience with Technology
The study included 74 students (35 male, 39 female) between the ages of 13 and 17 from the gymnasium "Ak niet". Of these students, 47.5% frequently used technology for language learning focused on ESP, 35% used it occasionally, and 17.5% rarely engaged with it. **Student Feedback on Using Technology for Developing ESP.** Most students (93%) reported no difficulties accessing online platforms outside of class, with 91.5% indicating that accessing them from home was easy. The majority found the platforms user-friendly, with 91% agreeing that the layout was clear and easy to navigate.

In terms of communication, over 90% of students felt comfortable sharing their ideas in online forums and chatting with their classmates, and they also found it convenient to interact with instructors digitally. Additionally, 95% appreciated the use of online exercises and quizzes, which they felt enhanced their ESP skills. Students highlighted the importance of self-discipline and computer literacy for effective use of these tools.

More than 97% expressed interest in using similar technology in future courses, and 92% believed that their language learning had improved due to the use of online platforms.

Discussion. Research Question 1. How are digital technologies currently being integrated into ESP programs?

Digital technologies have increasingly become integral to English for Specific Purposes (ESP) programs, transforming the ways in which specialized language is taught and learned. These technologies offer flexibility, personalization, and real-world application, catering to the specific needs of learners across various professional fields.

Platforms like Moodle, Blackboard, and Canvas are commonly used in ESP programs to deliver content, manage assignments, and provide structured learning environments. Teachers can tailor courses to include industry-specific materials, track student progress, and facilitate communication through forums and chats.

Mobile apps like Quizlet, Anki, and Memrise are popular tools in ESP programs, particularly for vocabulary acquisition in specific fields like medical, legal, or business English. These apps allow students to practice and retain technical terminology through interactive flashcards, quizzes, and games. On-the-Go Learning: Mobile learning apps provide students with the flexibility to engage with ESP content on their smartphones or tablets, making it easier to integrate language practice into their daily routines, especially for busy professionals.

ESP programs increasingly use multimedia content to expose learners to authentic language in professional contexts. Industry-specific YouTube channels, TED Talks, and podcasts help students immerse themselves in the language used in real-world professional environments. Gamification helps sustain student motivation by incorporating rewards and progress tracking, making language learning more engaging and less formal, which can be particularly beneficial for younger learners or those new to digital tools.

However, according to experts' opinion, in the educational system of Kazakhstan there are a few systemic problems that impede the full and high quality implementation of informatization of education:

- a large number of students in one class-set, what directly influences on the quality of the educational process;

- high demand among students for additional training due to the limited resources and infrastructure;

- the relatively low salaries of teachers and their significant extracurricular workload associated with the organization of the educational process and the assessment of student learning outcomes;

- lack of effective mechanisms for advanced training and retraining of teaching staff;

- a high level of bureaucratic processes that impede the timely adoption of managerial decisions, and, moreover, a low level of transparency of educational processes. [5]

Research Question 2: What impact do digital technologies have on learner engagement and motivation in ESP courses?

The integration of digital technologies into English for Specific Purposes (ESP) courses has significantly transformed the learning experience, particularly in terms of learner engagement and motivation. By offering more interactive, flexible, and personalized learning environments, these technologies cater to the diverse needs of learners in specialized fields, enhancing their enthusiasm and commitment to language acquisition.

Many ESP programs use gamified elements such as quizzes, badges, and challenges to engage learners. Platforms like Kahoot and Quizlet allow students to compete with peers while reinforcing specialized vocabulary and language structures in an enjoyable manner. This competitive yet fun environment enhances student participation and keeps them actively involved in the learning process.

Interactive content, such as videos, simulations, and podcasts, helps create a dynamic learning experience. ESP learners can watch industry-specific instructional videos, participate in virtual case studies, or listen to podcasts that cover real-world topics related to their field. This exposure to authentic materials keeps learners engaged by making the content more relevant and practical.

Virtual platforms like Microsoft Teams or Google Meet support group work and discussion forums, allowing students to interact in real-time. This fosters collaborative learning, which can significantly increase engagement as learners work together on tasks such as simulations or project-based assignments, much like they would in real-world professional settings.

Research Question 3: What challenges do educators face when integrating digital technologies into ESP instruction?

The integration of digital technologies into English for Specific Purposes (ESP) instruction has opened up numerous opportunities for enhancing learning experiences. However, educators face several challenges in successfully implementing these tools, ranging from technical and pedagogical hurdles to broader institutional and cultural issues. These challenges can affect the effectiveness of digital tools in improving language acquisition and skill development.

One of the primary challenges educators face is a lack of familiarity with digital tools and platforms. Many teachers, particularly those with more traditional teaching backgrounds, may not be adequately trained to use modern technologies in the classroom. This digital skill gap can limit their ability to create engaging content, use Learning Management Systems (LMS), or leverage mobile applications effectively.

While digital technologies offer immense potential to enhance ESP instruction, educators face several challenges in integrating these tools effectively. These challenges include a lack of digital literacy, time constraints for developing specialized content, unequal access to technology, and difficulties in providing personalized feedback and assessment. Конец формы Конец формы

Conclusion

The study concludes that digital technologies hold great promise for the future of ESP, offering innovative

solutions to enhance both teaching methodologies and learning experiences. However, challenges such as equitable access to technology, adequate teacher training, and the need for further research on long-term outcomes must be addressed to fully harness these possibilities. The future of ESP lies in the successful integration of digital technologies, which offer new opportunities for personalized, immersive, and collaborative learning. Both Kazakh and international researchers agree that the prospects for ESP development through digital tools are promising, but they also stress the importance of addressing challenges related to infrastructure, teacher training, and accessibility. With continued investment in digital education, ESP can play a crucial role in equipping learners with the specialized language skills needed in today's globalized world.

References:

1. A.S. Smagulova 1, R.M. Rakhimbayeva 2, M.S. Omarova 3 (2021). "The application of modern teaching tools and Internet technologies in the teaching of foreign languages" Almaty, Kazakhstan, 113-125
2. Angelica Bottaro 1 (2023) "Teaching English for Specific Purposes (ESP): What You Need To Know" <https://teflonline.teachaway.com/blogs/tefl-resources/teaching-esp-english-for-specific-purposes>. University of Toronto
3. Andrienko A. S.1 (2017) "English for specific purposes: retrospective analysis and prospects of development." Russia, Taganrog, 1175-1179
4. Beibitova M.C.1, (2020) "The role of digital technology in foreign language teaching." Abylai Khan KazUIR&WL, Almaty, Kazakhstan, 60-65
5. Bokayev B 1, Torebekova Z 2, Davletbayeva Z 3, (2020) "Implementation of information and communication technology in educational system of Kazakhstan: challenges and opportunities" Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan, 32-44
6. Shayakhmetova A.N 1, Saibekova N.U 2, (2021) "Methods of using distance learning for school-children in teaching English", Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Almaty, 126-135